

Role of Mass Media and Education

Ms.Rijumoni Chutia

Eastern Karbi Anglong College

Sarihajan, Karbi Anglong

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Abstract: Mass Media is any medium used to transmit mass communication. Radio, television, video camera, printed media like books, newspaper and magazines, the internet, teleconferencing, satellite communication and transmission all come in the category of mass communication. It aims to reach a very large market, such as the entire population of a country. Mass media can bring changes in our human society. It is play an important role for the development of education field. Mass media is providing a variety of information; people acquire different types of knowledge very quickly. Media helps in providing vocational and professional information to a larger group of the community. This paper will mainly base on secondary sources of data along with the presenters own observation.

Keywords: Mass media, Education, Role, Communication, development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mass media is a collective concept that refers to all media technologies, including the internet, television, newspapers, film and radio which are used for mass communication. In other words mass media stands dissemination of information, ideas and entertainment by the use of communication media. Mass media consists of the various means by which information reaches large numbers of people. Radio, television, video, cinema, printed media like books, newspaper and magazines and the internet, teleconferencing, satellite communication and transmission all come in the categories of mass communication. It aims to reach a very large market, such as the entire population of a country. Mass media are means of impersonal communication via some medium, imported through mediated situation. It is an instrument of communication reach large number of people with a common message. Mass media a predominant role in social change. Mass media can bring changes in our society. It is plays an important role for the development of education. There are different types of mass media present in our life. Mass media refers to different types of useful materials, devices and symbols that make the study of a subject more meaningful and interesting. Print media comprise newspaper, magazine, and newsletter books. Electronic media mainly includes television and radio. New-age media often refers to mobile phone, computer and the internet.

Mass media is the most significant channel which informs the public, provides information, generates political ideas, mobilizes political and social action groups and generally helps to shape the public policy agenda and priorities. The attitude and habits of people can change with the use of mass media. Media technology has been able to bring human beings closer. Increase communication and access information have made the world seem like a smaller place. Mass media use by the consumer industry to inform people about their products and services through advertising. Without advertising, the public will not know about various products and services which are available in the market as well as prices. Thus mass media helps industries and consumers.

Objectives:

It is study the role of mass media and education which is covered the following objectives-

1. To find out the role of mass media on education.
2. To find out the influence of mass media on education.
3. It also study, how does mass media effect on education.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study is based on general information and personal observation. Some information is collected from the secondary sources such as books, magazines, related articles, internet and newspaper etc.

Analysis of the theme:

Mass media is plays an important role in education. Though modern electronic techniques and technologies, mass media prove that education is really comprehensive and can't remind confined within the four walls of the class room. Irrespective of caste, colure, geographical, sociological and economical diversities, mass media proves as important means of providing education to all. Mankind gets a great deal of information from a widespread mass media. The roles of mass media in education are –

1. Providing a variety of information: media helps in disseminating a variety of information to the masses. People acquire different types of knowledge very quickly.
2. Providing vocational information: media help in providing vocational and professional information to a larger group of a community.
3. Spreading awareness and civic responsibilities: People can be aware of the different problem of the society and their role in the changing society through mass media. People clearly know their right and duties for the nation.
4. Educational programs: mass media helps in informing a suitable habit for different programs and they utilize their leisure time in a productive way. It also influences the behavior of people through different programs.
5. Role as non-formal agencies: media is called non formal agency due to its wide coverage on education items in systematic ways. It is believe that this media can substitute class room teaching in future.

Press, radio, motion picture, television etc. are mass media in education. These are technically called passive agencies of education. They indirectly influence the attitude and behavior of the people. They cover entertainment informatory propaganda, historical record, education and improvement of moral judgment and moral tone of the people. The radio is a valuable supplement to class teaching and learning. Educational broadcasting is a new experiment catching on well. Expert teaching in such diverse field of science, social studies, art, music, language, politics, current affairs and other areas can provide information and enrichment for people and for the teacher through school broadcaster. Television is a powerful land mark in the development of communication. Live programs and motion picture can be broadcaster on the television. Educational television includes all those programs whose primary aim interest is too educated rather than entertain. Television make possible for the talent of the best teacher to put at the disposal of all schools. Educational authorities can produce TV lesson made to their own requirement for specific local needs. In early times, the teacher was the only medium of communication for children. He taught his student orally. During the course of time the invention of the printing press, lead to the printing of books. Then comes newspapers. Now for quite some time new mass media like radio, television, internet is increasingly used in education. They reach large members and help in improving the quality of education.

3. CONCLUSION

Therefore mass media are the main means of educating the society. These are the cheapest and quickest means of the education for the people. The impact of motivation is very quick through mass media. The teacher must use the educational media and method effectively in the class room. It makes idea clear to the children and helps them acquire correct knowledge. It sends the information to remote place helps in distance learning. Therefore mass media is most important in education.

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